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Passive Model Predictive Control on a Two-body Self-Referenced Point Absorber Wave Energy Converter

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Abstract: Wave energy is nowadays one of the most promising renewable energy sources, however, wave energy technology has not reached the fully-commercial stage, yet. One key aspect to achieve this goal is to identify an effective control strategy for each selected Wave Energy Converter (WEC), in order to extract the maximum energy from the waves, while respecting the physical constraints of the device. Model Predictive Control (MPC) can inherently satisfy these requirements. Generally, MPC is formulated as a quadratic programming problem with linear constraints (e.g. on position, speed and Power Take-Off (PTO) force). Since, in the most general case, this control technique requires bidirectional power flow between the PTO system and the grid, it has similar characteristics as reactive control. This means that, under some operating conditions, the energy losses may be equivalent, or even larger, than the energy yielded. As many WECs are designed to only allow unidirectional power flow, it is necessary to set nonlinear constraints. This makes the optimization problem significantly more expensive in terms of computational time. This work proposes two MPC control strategies applied to a two-body point absorber that address this issue from two different perspectives: a) adapting the MPC formulation to passive loading strategy and b) adapting linear constraints in the MPC in order to only allow an unidirectional power flow. The results show that the two alternative proposals have similar performance in terms of computational time compared to the regular MPC and obtain considerably more power than the linear passive control, thus proving to be a good option for unidirectional PTO systems.

Keywords: wave energy converter; model predictive control; passive control, two-body point absorber

1. Introduction

Ocean energy and particularly wave energy is nowadays one of the most promising, but still underutilized, renewable energy sources that can be commercially exploited to provide power to the electrical grid [1]. One key aspect to achieve this goal is an efficient control strategy which absorbs maximum energy from the waves, while respecting the physical constraints of each WEC.

Linear control strategies are still the most used for WECs. **They have been deeply studied in the WEC literature and provide a reliable, robust, and efficient control in most cases.** Among them, in reactive control the force applied by the PTO system is the sum of multiple components, proportional to the position, velocity and acceleration of the WEC, respectively [2]. This strategy typically requires the PTO to be oversized and work both as generator and motor, which can have a negative impact on its

31 efficiency [3]. In reactive control, the optimal velocity profile is a function of the future wave excitation
32 force, so, this velocity cannot be determined optimally in practice. For this reason, suboptimal control
33 strategies based on causal functions are used [4]. Moreover, reactive control presents drawbacks from
34 the energy perspective, requiring large bidirectional power flows between the WEC and the PTO [5].
35 In addition, displacements and velocities may be too high and they would have to be considered in
36 the mechanical design, and managed in the WEC operation.

37 Passive control, is another strategy where the force applied by the PTO is just proportional
38 to the WEC velocity, which allows an unidirectional power exchange, from the WEC to the PTO.
39 Compared to reactive control, passive control presents the following advantages: a) unidirectional
40 instead of bidirectional power flow means moderate losses, b) the power peaks and the amplitude
41 of the oscillations are lower, so the installation becomes cheaper and less critical. The main passive
42 control drawback is the limited power capture compared to reactive, especially for wave profiles far
43 from the natural response of the WEC.

44 The Model Predictive Control (MPC) is being used with certain success on Wave Energy
45 Converters, because its formulation is optimal in terms of energy extraction and is able to inherently
46 manage physical constraints [6], [7]. This technique requires a WEC model and an excitation force
47 prediction within a predefined time interval in order to predict the next control action on the PTO force
48 [8]. This action is obtained optimizing an objective function over the prediction horizon. Generally,
49 MPC on WEC applications is formulated as a quadratic programming (QP) problem with linear
50 constraints, where the objective function is the extracted energy and the constraints are the position,
51 speed and PTO force [9], [10]. Since in the most general case this control technique requires bidirectional
52 power flow between the PTO system and the grid, it has similar disadvantages as reactive control: a)
53 PTO working as generator and motor, b) increase of PTO losses and, c) reduction of efficiency.

54 Few MPC applications to WECs have addressed the problem of restricting the power flow
55 direction from the WEC to the PTO, thus allowing its application to a broader range of existing
56 WECs. The reason for this gap is that allowing this unidirectional energy flow using QP in MPC,
57 requires setting nonlinear constraints. This turns the QP optimization with linear constraints into
58 a Nonlinear Programming (NLP) problem with nonlinear constraints, making the computational
59 effort significantly higher [6]. Among the few contributions addressing the problem in the available
60 literature, O'Sullivan and Lightbody [11] restricted the power flow direction by means of a nonlinear
61 constraint function that depends on the speed, flux, resistance and current of an electrical PTO. In
62 order to allow just unidirectional power flow, Paparella and Ringwood [12], [13] proposed a MPC-like
63 strategy using pseudo-spectral control with truncated Fourier series as orthogonal base in order to
64 handle the nonlinear power constraints in a more efficient way. Both proposals have, however, the
65 same drawback: nonlinear constraints imply higher processing time to solve the optimization problem.
66 Tom and Yeung [14] study a permanent magnet generator as PTO with a passive non-linear MPC
67 control strategy. They define the PTO force as a linear function of the velocity ($F_{pto}=b_g v(t)$) and
68 integrate the dynamic of the WEC inside the objective function from a numerical perspective using
69 the Berkeley Library for Optimization Modeling software (BLOM) on a Matlab/Simulink model. This
70 work proposes two independent MPC control strategies applied to a two-body self-reference point
71 absorber that address this issue from two different perspectives: a) adapting the MPC formulation to
72 achieve passive loading strategy as the work by Tom and Yeung ([14]), but integrating analytically the
73 dynamic of the WEC inside the objective function and b) re-formulating the linear constraints in the
74 MPC in order to only allow an unidirectional energy flow. The results show that the proposed control
75 strategies have similar performance compared to the regular MPC in terms of computational time and
76 they extract considerably more power than the classical passive control.

77 This paper is divided into 6 sections. Section 2 presents the model of the two-body self-reference
78 point absorber. Section 3 shows the traditional MPC approach considering linear and nonlinear
79 constraints. The two MPC proposals based on passivity (to prevent bidirectional energy flow) are

80 formulated in section 4 and 5, respectively. Section 6 presents the analysis of the results and section 7
 81 the conclusions.

82 2. Model of the two-body self-reference point absorber WEC

83 The WEC model used in this work and shown in Fig. 1 was developed within the IMAGINE
 84 project [15] funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme. This WEC is a two-body
 85 self-referenced point absorber formed by an external floater ring that moves with respect to an internal
 86 cylindrical spar attached to the sea bed by means of a mooring. This relative movement is exploited
 87 by the PTO to extract power from the WEC. The PTO system is a direct-drive device in which a
 88 recirculating ball screw is coupled with a three-phase Permanent Magnet Generator (PMG) as shown
 89 in Fig. 2 [16] and described in [17]. The linear motion of the ball screw is converted into the nut rotary
 90 motion. Being the ball nut connected to the rotor of the permanent magnet generator, its mechanical
 91 rotational energy is directly converted in electricity.

Figure 1. Two-body self-reference point absorber wave energy converter

Figure 2. Electro-mechanical ball-screw PTO concept [16]

Linear wave theory has been used in order to model the wave profile. According to the Cumming's formulation, the dynamic eqs. (1) and (2) describe the 2-body wave energy converter motion in heave mode [18]:

$$(m_1 + A_{11}^{\infty})\ddot{z}_1(t) + F_{r1}(t) + k_{h1}z_1(t) + (b_{fr} + b_{v1})\dot{z}_1(t) - b_{fr}\dot{z}_2(t) = F_{e1}(t) + F_{pto}(t) \quad (1)$$

$$(m_2 + A_{22}^{\infty})\ddot{z}_2(t) + F_{r2}(t) + (k_{h2} + k_m)z_2(t) + (b_{fr} + b_{v2})\dot{z}_2(t) - b_{fr}\dot{z}_1(t) = F_{e2}(t) - F_{pto}(t) \quad (2)$$

where ρ is the water density, g is the gravity acceleration, k_m is the mooring stiffness, b_{fr} is the PTO friction coefficient and $F_{pto}(t)$ is the PTO force. For the body i , $k_{hi} = \rho g S_i$ is the hydrostatic coefficient, m_i is the mass, S_i is the body transversal area, b_{vi} is the viscosity coefficient, A_{ii}^{∞} is the added mass at infinite frequency, $F_{ri}(t)$ is the radiation force, $F_{ei}(t)$ is the excitation force and $z_i(t)$, $\dot{z}_i(t)$ and $\ddot{z}_i(t)$ are the position, speed and acceleration. In the paragraph above the subscript i is 1 when referred to body 1 (floater) and 2 when referred to body 2 (spar). In addition, the PTO mass is considered negligible compared to m_1 and m_2 .

2.1. Space state model in continuous time

Both radiation forces $F_{r1}(t)$ and $F_{r2}(t)$ above can be modeled by means of state space equations based on [19]. The space state models used for the floater and the spar will be the following third and second order systems, respectively:

$$\dot{\mathbf{U}}_1(t) = \mathbf{A}_{r1}\mathbf{U}_1(t) + \mathbf{B}_{r1}\dot{z}_1(t) \quad (3)$$

$$F_{r1}(t) = \mathbf{C}_{r1}\mathbf{U}_1(t) \quad (4)$$

where

$$\mathbf{A}_{r1} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{r1}(1,1) & a_{r1}(1,2) & a_{r1}(1,3) \\ a_{r1}(2,1) & a_{r1}(2,2) & a_{r1}(2,3) \\ a_{r1}(3,1) & a_{r1}(3,2) & a_{r1}(3,3) \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{B}_{r1} = \begin{bmatrix} b_{r1}(1) \\ b_{r1}(2) \\ b_{r1}(3) \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{U}_1(t) = \begin{bmatrix} u_{11}(t) \\ u_{21}(t) \\ u_{31}(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{C}_{r1}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} c_{r1}(1) & c_{r1}(2) & c_{r1}(3) \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

and

$$\dot{\mathbf{U}}_2(t) = \mathbf{A}_{r2}\mathbf{U}_2(t) + \mathbf{B}_{r2}\dot{z}_2(t) \quad (7)$$

$$F_{r2}(t) = \mathbf{C}_{r2}\mathbf{U}_2(t) \quad (8)$$

where

$$\mathbf{A}_{r2} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{r2}(1,1) & a_{r2}(1,2) \\ a_{r2}(2,1) & a_{r2}(2,2) \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{B}_{r2} = \begin{bmatrix} b_{r2}(1) \\ b_{r2}(2) \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{U}_2(t) = \begin{bmatrix} u_{12}(t) \\ u_{22}(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{C}_{r2} = \begin{bmatrix} c_{r2}(1) & c_{r2}(2) \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

The states of the radiation forces $F_{r1}(t)$ and $F_{r2}(t)$ are $\mathbf{U}_1(t) = [u_{11}(t) \ u_{21}(t) \ u_{31}(t)]^T$ and $\mathbf{U}_2(t) = [u_{12}(t) \ u_{22}(t)]^T$ respectively. The dynamics described by the system of differential equations from (1) to (10) can be modeled by means of the following state space equations [18], [19]:

$$\dot{\mathbf{X}}(t) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{X}(t) + \mathbf{B}_{e1}F_{e1}(t) + \mathbf{B}_{e2}F_{e2}(t) + \mathbf{B}_{pto}F_{pto}(t) \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{Y}(t) = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{X}(t) = [z_1(t) - z_2(t) \ z_1(t) - \dot{z}_2(t)]^T \quad (12)$$

where

$$\mathbf{X}(t) = [u_{11}(t) \ u_{21}(t) \ u_{31}(t) \ z_1(t) \ \dot{z}_1(t) \ u_{12}(t) \ u_{22}(t) \ z_2(t) \ \dot{z}_2(t)]^T \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{r1}(1,1) & a_{r1}(1,2) & a_{r1}(1,3) & 0 & b_{r1}(1) & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a_{r1}(2,1) & a_{r1}(2,2) & a_{r1}(2,3) & 0 & b_{r1}(2) & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a_{r1}(3,1) & a_{r1}(3,2) & a_{r1}(3,3) & 0 & b_{r1}(3) & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{c_{r1}(1)}{A_1} & \frac{c_{r1}(2)}{A_1} & \frac{c_{r1}(3)}{A_1} & \frac{k_{h1}}{A_1} & \frac{b_{v1}+b_{fr}}{A_1} & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{b_{fr}}{A_1} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & a_{r2}(1,1) & a_{r2}(1,2) & 0 & b_{r2}(1) \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & a_{r2}(2,1) & a_{r2}(2,2) & 0 & b_{r2}(2) \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{b_{fr}}{A_2} & \frac{c_{r2}(1)}{A_2} & \frac{c_{r2}(2)}{A_2} & \frac{k_{h2}+k_m}{A_2} & \frac{b_{fr}+b_{v2}}{A_2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

$$\mathbf{B}_{e1} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{1}{A_1} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (15)$$

$$\mathbf{B}_{e2} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{1}{A_2} \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (16)$$

$$\mathbf{B}_{pto} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{1}{A_1} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{A_2} \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (17)$$

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

103 and $A_1 = -(m_1 + A_{11}^\infty)$, $A_2 = -(m_2 + A_{22}^\infty)$, $z_1(t) - z_2(t)$ is the position of the PTO and $\dot{z}_1(t) - \dot{z}_2(t)$
 104 is its velocity. Numerical values of the WEC parameters present from eq. (3) to eq. (18) can be found in
 105 Appendix A.

106 2.2. Space state model in discrete time

107 In order to design an MPC strategy, the discretization of the space state model is necessary. In
 108 this section, two space state models in discrete time are presented. The first one uses the discretized
 109 PTO force, $F_{pto}(k)$, (where k is the discretized time variable) as control signal and the second uses the
 110 variation of the discretized PTO force between successive time instants, $\Delta F_{pto}(k+1) = F_{pto}(k+1) -$
 111 $F_{pto}(k)$ including the PTO force, $F_{pto}(k)$, as a system state. Both approaches are equivalent and are
 112 used as needed by the proposals. The first approach will make as a easy to rewrite the control variable
 113 $F_{pto}(k)$ by $b_{pto}(z_1(t) - z_2(t))$ in order to formulate a first passive MPC strategy as a function of the b_{pto}
 114 parameter. The second MPC approach will allow to constraint the variation of the PTO force between
 115 time steps and at the same time assign the linear constraints on the state variables speed and PTO
 116 force.

117 2.2.1. First approach: PTO force $F_{pto}(k)$ as control signal

118 Using the discrete solution of the state space eq. (11) described by Chen [20] and considering the
 119 variables constant between samples, in the zero-order hold approximation, the following discrete state
 120 space equation is obtained:

$$\mathbf{X}(k+1) = \mathbf{A}_d \mathbf{X}(k) + \mathbf{B}_{de1} F_{e1}(k) + \mathbf{B}_{de2} F_{e2}(k) + \mathbf{B}_{dpto} F_{pto}(k) \quad (19)$$

$$\mathbf{Y}(k) = \mathbf{C}_d \mathbf{X}(k) = [z_1(k) - z_2(k) \quad \dot{z}_1(k) - \dot{z}_2(k)]^T \quad (20)$$

where $\mathbf{A}_d = e^{\mathbf{A}T}$, $\mathbf{B}_{de1} = \mathbf{A}^{-1}(e^{\mathbf{A}T} - I)\mathbf{B}_{e1}$, $\mathbf{B}_{de2} = \mathbf{A}^{-1}(e^{\mathbf{A}T} - I)\mathbf{B}_{e2}$, $\mathbf{B}_{dpto} = \mathbf{A}^{-1}(e^{\mathbf{A}T} - I)\mathbf{B}_{pto}$,
 $\mathbf{C}_d = \mathbf{C}$, $F_{pto}(k)$ is the discretized PTO force, $F_{e1}(k)$ and $F_{e2}(k)$ are the discretized excitation forces on
 both floater and spar and $\mathbf{X}(k)$ is the discretized state vector:

$$\mathbf{X}(k) = [y_{11}(k) \quad y_{21}(k) \quad y_{31}(k) \quad z_1(k) \quad \dot{z}_1(k) \quad y_{12}(k) \quad y_{22}(k) \quad z_2(k) \quad \dot{z}_2(k)]^T \quad (21)$$

121 2.2.2. Second approach: Variation of the PTO force $\Delta F_{pto}(k)$ as control signal

122 Cretel et al [21] rewrite the discrete state space formulation of eq. (19) including the excitation
123 forces and the PTO force as states. In addition, incremental values of the excitation forces $\Delta F_{e1}(k+1)$,
124 $\Delta F_{e2}(k+1)$ and PTO force $\Delta F_{pto}(k+1)$ are the new inputs (eqs. (22)-(24)).

$$F_{e1}(k+1) = F_{e1}(k) + \Delta F_{e1}(k+1) \quad (22)$$

$$F_{e2}(k+1) = F_{e2}(k) + \Delta F_{e2}(k+1) \quad (23)$$

$$F_{pto}(k+1) = F_{pto}(k) + \Delta F_{pto}(k+1) \quad (24)$$

The state space equations in terms of the new augmented state vector are:

$$\mathbf{W}(k+1) = \mathbf{A}_w \cdot \mathbf{W}(k) + \mathbf{B}_{w1} \cdot \Delta F_{e1}(k+1) + \mathbf{B}_{w2} \cdot \Delta F_{e2}(k+1) + \mathbf{B}_{wpto} \cdot \Delta F_{pto}(k+1) \quad (25)$$

$$\mathbf{V}(k) = \mathbf{C}_w \cdot \mathbf{W}(k) \quad (26)$$

where

$$\mathbf{W}(k) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{X}(k) \\ F_{e1}(k) \\ F_{e2}(k) \\ F_{pto}(k) \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{V}(k) = \begin{bmatrix} z_1(k) - z_2(k) \\ z_1(k) - z_2(k) \\ F_{pto}(k) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{A}_w = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_d & \mathbf{B}_{de1} & \mathbf{B}_{de2} & \mathbf{B}_{dpto} \\ 0_{1,9} & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0_{1,9} & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0_{1,9} & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{B}_{w1} = \begin{bmatrix} 0_{9,1} \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{B}_{w2} = \begin{bmatrix} 0_{9,1} \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{B}_{wpto} = \begin{bmatrix} 0_{9,1} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{C}_w = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{C}_d & 0_{2,1} & 0_{2,1} & 0_{2,1} \\ 0_{1,9} & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

125 and $0_{x,y}$ is a null elements matrix with x rows and y columns.

126 Setting the incremental values of the PTO force $\Delta F_{pto}(k+1)$ as a control signal, allows avoiding
127 abrupt changes in the PTO force between consecutive control actions using an additional linear
128 constraint in the MPC optimization problem. This new constraint is explained in section 3.3.

129 3. Traditional Model Predictive Control

130 MPC gets an optimal control for optimizing an objective function (minimization or maximization)
131 over a finite future time horizon. In order to implement an MPC strategy successfully, it is necessary
132 [22]: a) a mathematical model of the system to predict the output on the future horizon, b) an objective
133 function to obtain an optimal control series over the future horizon using an optimization procedure
134 with constraints, and c) a receding strategy where at each instant, the first sample of the optimal control
135 series calculated by the optimization is applied.

136 3.1. Prediction Equations of the Traditional MPC

In order to get the prediction equations, the methodology shown by Rossiter [23] is used. This methodology is based on the discrete state space eqs. (25) obtained by assuming the variation of the PTO force $\Delta F_{pto}(k)$ between two consecutive time instants as the control signal (second approach in section 2.2):

$$\underline{\mathbf{V}}(k) = \mathbf{P}\mathbf{W}(k) + \mathbf{H}_{e1} \underline{\Delta F_{e1}}(k) + \mathbf{H}_{e2} \underline{\Delta F_{e2}}(k) + \mathbf{H}_{pto} \underline{\Delta F_{pto}}(k) \quad (27)$$

137 where

$$\underline{\Delta \mathbf{F}_{e1}}(k) = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta F_{e1}(k+1) \\ \Delta F_{e1}(k+2) \\ \Delta F_{e1}(k+3) \\ \vdots \\ \Delta F_{e1}(k+n_h) \end{bmatrix}, \quad \underline{\Delta \mathbf{F}_{e2}}(k) = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta F_{e2}(k+1) \\ \Delta F_{e2}(k+2) \\ \Delta F_{e2}(k+3) \\ \vdots \\ \Delta F_{e2}(k+n_h) \end{bmatrix}, \quad \underline{\Delta \mathbf{F}_{pto}}(k) = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta F_{pto}(k+1) \\ \Delta F_{pto}(k+2) \\ \Delta F_{pto}(k+3) \\ \vdots \\ \Delta F_{pto}(k+n_h) \end{bmatrix} \quad (28)$$

$$\underline{\mathbf{V}}(k) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{V}(k+1) \\ \mathbf{V}(k+2) \\ \mathbf{V}(k+3) \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{V}(k+n_h) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} (z_1(k+1) - z_2(k+1), z_1(k+1) - z_2(k+1), F_{pto}(k+1))^T \\ (z_1(k+2) - z_2(k+2), z_1(k+2) - z_2(k+2), F_{pto}(k+2))^T \\ (z_1(k+3) - z_2(k+3), z_1(k+3) - z_2(k+3), F_{pto}(k+3))^T \\ \vdots \\ (z_1(k+n_h) - z_2(k+n_h), z_1(k+n_h) - z_2(k+n_h), F_{pto}(k+n_h))^T \end{bmatrix} \quad (29)$$

138

$$\mathbf{P} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{A}_w \\ \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{A}_w^2 \\ \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{A}_w^3 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{A}_w^{n_h} \end{bmatrix} \quad (30)$$

$$\mathbf{H}_{e1} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{B}_{w1} & 0_{3,1} & 0_{3,1} & \cdots & 0_{3,1} \\ \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{A}_w \mathbf{B}_{w1} & \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{B}_{w1} & 0_{3,1} & \cdots & 0_{3,1} \\ \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{A}_w^2 \mathbf{B}_{w1} & \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{A}_w \mathbf{B}_{w1} & \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{B}_{w1} & \cdots & 0_{3,1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{A}_w^{n_h-1} \mathbf{B}_{w1} & \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{A}_w^{n_h-2} \mathbf{B}_{w1} & \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{A}_w^{n_h-3} \mathbf{B}_{w1} & \cdots & \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{B}_{w1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (31)$$

$$\mathbf{H}_{e2} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{B}_{w2} & 0_{3,1} & 0_{3,1} & \cdots & 0_{3,1} \\ \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{A}_w \mathbf{B}_{w2} & \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{B}_{w2} & 0_{3,1} & \cdots & 0_{3,1} \\ \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{A}_w^2 \mathbf{B}_{w2} & \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{A}_w \mathbf{B}_{w2} & \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{B}_{w2} & \cdots & 0_{3,1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{A}_w^{n_h-1} \mathbf{B}_{w2} & \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{A}_w^{n_h-2} \mathbf{B}_{w2} & \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{A}_w^{n_h-3} \mathbf{B}_{w2} & \cdots & \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{B}_{w2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (32)$$

$$\mathbf{H}_{pto} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{B}_{wpto} & 0_{3,1} & 0_{3,1} & \cdots & 0_{3,1} \\ \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{A}_w \mathbf{B}_{wpto} & \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{B}_{wpto} & 0_{3,1} & \cdots & 0_{3,1} \\ \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{A}_w^2 \mathbf{B}_{wpto} & \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{A}_w \mathbf{B}_{wpto} & \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{B}_{wpto} & \cdots & 0_{3,1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{A}_w^{n_h-1} \mathbf{B}_{wpto} & \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{A}_w^{n_h-2} \mathbf{B}_{wpto} & \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{A}_w^{n_h-3} \mathbf{B}_{wpto} & \cdots & \mathbf{C}_w \mathbf{B}_{wpto} \end{bmatrix} \quad (33)$$

139 and n_h is the sample number of the prediction horizon.

140 3.2. Objective Function of the Traditional MPC Control

The objective function $J(k)$ to be minimized at each time instant, k , will be the opposite of the average power absorbed by the PTO over the prediction horizon.

$$J(k) = -\frac{1}{n_h} \sum_{i=1}^{n_h} F_{pto}(k+i)(\dot{z}_1(k+i) - \dot{z}_2(k+i)) \quad (34)$$

The objective function above can be rewritten in terms of the future output $\underline{\mathbf{V}}(k)$ of eq. (27).

$$J(k) = -\frac{1}{2} \underline{\mathbf{V}}(k)^T Q_1 \underline{\mathbf{V}}(k) \quad (35)$$

141 where Q_1 is the following square matrix with order $3n_h$.

$$Q_1 = \begin{bmatrix} M & 0_{3,3} & \cdots & 0_{3,3} \\ 0_{3,3} & M & \cdots & 0_{3,3} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0_{3,3} & 0_{3,3} & \cdots & M \end{bmatrix} \quad (36)$$

142 with

$$M_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (37)$$

Finally, substituting eq. (27) in eq. (35), the following MPC objective function of a typical quadratic programming problem is obtained:

$$J = \frac{1}{2} \underline{\Delta \mathbf{F}}_{pto}(k)^T \mathbf{H}_{pto}^T Q_1 \mathbf{H}_{pto} \underline{\Delta \mathbf{F}}_{pto}(k) + (\mathbf{PW}(k) + \mathbf{H}_{e1} \underline{\Delta \mathbf{F}}_{e1}(k) + \mathbf{H}_{e2} \underline{\Delta \mathbf{F}}_{e2}(k))^T Q_1 \mathbf{H}_{pto} \underline{\Delta \mathbf{F}}_{pto}(k) \quad (38)$$

143 3.3. Constraints on the Objective Function for the Traditional MPC

In order to set maximum and minimum values to the force, velocity, position and force increment of the PTO, linear constraints on the MPC objective function can be added to the optimization problem [7]. Restrictions on the PTO force increments can be simply formulated as:

$$\underline{\Delta \mathbf{F}}_{pto}^{min} < \underline{\Delta \mathbf{F}}_{pto}(k) < \underline{\Delta \mathbf{F}}_{pto}^{max} \quad (39)$$

On the other hand, constraints on the position, speed and PTO force can be set in the prediction vector $\underline{\mathbf{V}}(k)$ (eq.(29)) and expressed by means of eq. (27) as a linear matrix relationship as a function of the control variable $\underline{\Delta \mathbf{F}}_{pto}(k)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{\mathbf{V}}(k)^{min} - \mathbf{PW}(k) - \mathbf{H}_{e1} \underline{\Delta \mathbf{F}}_{e1}(k) - \mathbf{H}_{e2} \underline{\Delta \mathbf{F}}_{e2}(k) < \mathbf{H}_{pto} \underline{\Delta \mathbf{F}}_{pto}(k) < \dots \\ \dots \underline{\mathbf{V}}(k)^{max} - \mathbf{PW}(k) - \mathbf{H}_{e1} \underline{\Delta \mathbf{F}}_{e1}(k) - \mathbf{H}_{e2} \underline{\Delta \mathbf{F}}_{e2}(k) \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

144 Regarding the restrictions defined in eqs. (39) and (40), the optimization problem of eq. (38)
145 becomes a quadratic programming problem with linear constraints.

146 3.4. Non-Linear Constraints on the Objective Function for the Traditional MPC to get Passivity

A direct manner to get unidirectional power flow in the MPC optimization problem of the eq. (38) is constraining the PTO power at each instant by means of the product between PTO force and velocity [11]. However, as it was mentioned in section 1, this approach is expensive in terms of computational time, hence it provides a solution to the passivity problem that is not viable for real-time applications, thus limiting its practical usability. In the following, the PTO power constraint is enforced at each time instant, k , by means of the product between PTO force and velocity:

$$P_{pto}(k+i) = F_{pto}(k+i)(\dot{z}_1(k+i) - \dot{z}_2(k+i)) > 0 \quad for \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n_h \quad (41)$$

147 The MPC objective function of eq. (38) and the non-linear constraint of eq. (41) define a nonlinear
148 programming problem (NLP) with nonlinear constraints.

149 4. Passive MPC proposal 1: Adapting MPC formulation to passive loading strategy

One of the passive control strategies is the resistive load control where the PTO force just depends on the PTO velocity in the following linear way:

$$F_{pto}(t) = b_{pto}(\dot{z}_1(t) - \dot{z}_2(t)) \quad (42)$$

150 In order to constraint the PTO force to take values such that the control is passive, eq. (42) is
151 discretized and substituted in the discrete model of eq. (19), which was obtained by using the PTO
152 force $F_{pto}(k)$ as the control signal (first approach in section 2.2):

$$\mathbf{X}(k+1) = \mathbf{A}_d\mathbf{X}(k) + \mathbf{B}_{de1}F_{e1}(k) + \mathbf{B}_{de2}F_{e2}(k) + \mathbf{B}_{dpto}b_{pto}(\dot{z}_1(k) - \dot{z}_2(k)) \quad (43)$$

153 The last term in eq. (43) can be expressed using the state space vector $\mathbf{X}(k)$. From eq. (21):

$$\dot{z}_1(k) - \dot{z}_2(k) = \mathbf{B}_f\mathbf{X}(k) \quad (44)$$

where

$$\mathbf{B}_f = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (45)$$

154 Finally, the discrete space state model can be formulated as:

$$\mathbf{X}(k+1) = \mathbf{A}_{d2}\mathbf{X}(k) + \mathbf{B}_{de1}F_{e1}(k) + \mathbf{B}_{de2}F_{e2}(k) \quad (46)$$

$$\mathbf{Y}(k) = \mathbf{C}_d\mathbf{X}(k) = [z_1(k) - z_2(k) \quad \dot{z}_1(k) - \dot{z}_2(k)]^T \quad (47)$$

where

$$\mathbf{A}_{d2} = \mathbf{A}_d + \mathbf{B}_{dpto}b_{pto}\mathbf{B}_f \quad (48)$$

155 Notice that matrix \mathbf{A}_{d2} is function of b_{pto} . Eqs. (46) and (47) model a two-body point absorber
156 with passive control in discrete time, where the PTO damping is defined by b_{pto} .

157 4.1. Prediction Equations of the Passive MPC Proposal 1

The main idea of this passive MPC proposal is to determine the PTO damping at each time instant, k , for the WEC modeled by eqs. (46) and (47). This means that:

$$b_{pto} = b_{pto}(k) \quad (49)$$

In order to do so, an optimization problem will be formulated using the discrete system model of eqs. (46) and (47), and prediction of the excitation forces on a future horizon. Based on the discrete state space eqs.(46) and (47) and using the methodology shown by Rossiter [23], the following prediction equations for the passive MPC formulation can be obtained:

$$\underline{\mathbf{Y}}(k) = \mathbf{P}\mathbf{X}(k) + \mathbf{H}_{e1}\underline{\mathbf{F}}_{e1}(k) + \mathbf{H}_{e2}\underline{\mathbf{F}}_{e2}(k) \quad (50)$$

158 where

$$\underline{\mathbf{F}}_{e1}(k) = \begin{bmatrix} F_{e1}(k+1) \\ F_{e1}(k+2) \\ F_{e1}(k+3) \\ \vdots \\ F_{e1}(k+n_h) \end{bmatrix}, \quad \underline{\mathbf{F}}_{e2}(k) = \begin{bmatrix} F_{e2}(k+1) \\ F_{e2}(k+2) \\ F_{e2}(k+3) \\ \vdots \\ F_{e2}(k+n_h) \end{bmatrix}, \quad \underline{\mathbf{Y}}(k) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Y}(k+1) \\ \mathbf{Y}(k+2) \\ \mathbf{Y}(k+3) \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{Y}(k+n_h) \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{P} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{C}_d \mathbf{A}_{d2} \\ \mathbf{C}_d \mathbf{A}_{d2}^2 \\ \mathbf{C}_d \mathbf{A}_{d2}^3 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{C}_d \mathbf{A}_{d2}^{n_h} \end{bmatrix} \quad (51)$$

$$\mathbf{H}_{e1} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{C}_d \mathbf{B}_{de1} & 0_{3,1} & 0_{3,1} & \cdots & 0_{3,1} \\ \mathbf{C}_d \mathbf{A}_{d2} \mathbf{B}_{de1} & \mathbf{C}_d \mathbf{B}_{de1} & 0_{3,1} & \cdots & 0_{3,1} \\ \mathbf{C}_d \mathbf{A}_{d2}^2 \mathbf{B}_{de1} & \mathbf{C}_d \mathbf{A}_{d2} \mathbf{B}_{de1} & \mathbf{C}_d \mathbf{B}_{de1} & \cdots & 0_{3,1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{C}_d \mathbf{A}_{d2}^{n_h-1} \mathbf{B}_{de1} & \mathbf{C}_d \mathbf{A}_{d2}^{n_h-2} \mathbf{B}_{de1} & \mathbf{C}_d \mathbf{A}_{d2}^{n_h-3} \mathbf{B}_{de1} & \cdots & \mathbf{C}_d \mathbf{B}_{de1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (52)$$

$$\mathbf{H}_{e2} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{C}_d \mathbf{B}_{de2} & 0_{3,1} & 0_{3,1} & \cdots & 0_{3,1} \\ \mathbf{C}_d \mathbf{A}_{d2} \mathbf{B}_{de2} & \mathbf{C}_d \mathbf{B}_{de2} & 0_{3,1} & \cdots & 0_{3,1} \\ \mathbf{C}_d \mathbf{A}_{d2}^2 \mathbf{B}_{de2} & \mathbf{C}_d \mathbf{A}_{d2} \mathbf{B}_{de2} & \mathbf{C}_d \mathbf{B}_{de2} & \cdots & 0_{3,1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{C}_d \mathbf{A}_{d2}^{n_h-1} \mathbf{B}_{de2} & \mathbf{C}_d \mathbf{A}_{d2}^{n_h-2} \mathbf{B}_{de2} & \mathbf{C}_d \mathbf{A}_{d2}^{n_h-3} \mathbf{B}_{de2} & \cdots & \mathbf{C}_d \mathbf{B}_{de2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (53)$$

159 Notice that the matrices \mathbf{P} , \mathbf{H}_{e1} and \mathbf{H}_{e2} in eqs. (50)-(53) depend on \mathbf{A}_{d2} that is function of $b_{pto}(k)$
160 (eqs. (48)-(49)). It means that these matrices change in each time instant, k , as $b_{pto}(k)$ changes.

161 4.2. Objective Function of the Passive MPC Proposal 1

In passive control, the opposite of the average power absorbed at each time instant, k , by the PTO over the prediction horizon can be formulated as:

$$J(k) = -\frac{1}{n_h} \sum_{i=1}^{n_h} b_{pto}(k+i) (\dot{z}_1(k+i) - \dot{z}_2(k+i))^2 \quad (54)$$

Eq. (54) can be rewritten in term of the future output $\underline{\mathbf{Y}}(k)$ from eq. (50).

$$J(k) = -\frac{b_{pto}(k)}{n_h} \underline{\mathbf{Y}}(k)^T \mathbf{Q}_2 \underline{\mathbf{Y}}(k) \quad (55)$$

162 where \mathbf{Q}_2 is the following square matrix with order $2n_h$.

$$\mathbf{Q}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} M & 0_{2,2} & \cdots & 0_{2,2} \\ 0_{2,2} & M & \cdots & 0_{2,2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0_{2,2} & 0_{2,2} & \cdots & M \end{bmatrix} \quad (56)$$

163 with

$$M_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (57)$$

164 Substituting eq. (50) in eq. (55) and considering the dependence of \mathbf{P} , \mathbf{H}_{e1} and \mathbf{H}_{e2} on $b_{pto}(k)$, the
 165 objective function of eq. (54) can be expressed as:

$$J(k) = -b_{pto}(k) \left[\mathbf{P}[b_{pto}(k)]\mathbf{X}(k) + \mathbf{H}_{e1}[b_{pto}(k)]\underline{\mathbf{F}}_{e1}(k) + \mathbf{H}_{e2}[b_{pto}(k)]\underline{\mathbf{F}}_{e2}(k) \right]^T \cdot Q \dots$$

$$\dots \left[\mathbf{P}[b_{pto}(k)]\mathbf{X}(k) + \mathbf{H}_{e1}[b_{pto}(k)]\underline{\mathbf{F}}_{e1}(k) + \mathbf{H}_{e2}[b_{pto}(k)]\underline{\mathbf{F}}_{e2}(k) \right] \quad (58)$$

166 where at each time instant, k , the only unknown variable to be determined is the PTO damping $b_{pto}(k)$.
 167 The optimization problem of the eq. (58) is an one-variable NLP without constraint.

168 4.3. Constraints on the Objective Function of the Passive MPC Proposal 1

169 Although there is no constraint in the optimization of the objective function given in eq. (58), the
 170 positive sign of $b_{pto}(k)$ at each time instant k should be verified.

171 5. Passive MPC Proposal 2: Adapting linear constraints in the MPC to get passivity

172 This passive MPC proposal uses the same objective function as the traditional MPC (eq. (38)).
 173 Unlike the first proposal in section 4, which determines PTO damping $b_{pto}(k)$ at each time instant,
 174 this MPC optimization problem leads to estimate a PTO force series over the prediction horizon at
 175 each time instant. Passive control is imposed by properly managing the linear constraints defined in
 176 eqs. (39) and (40). The idea is to define speed and PTO force constraints at each time instant over the
 177 prediction horizon in such way that the product between speed and PTO force is positive.

178 5.1. Prediction Equations of the Passive MPC Proposal 2

179 This proposal uses the same prediction eqs. (27) as the traditional MPC.

180 5.2. Objective Function of the Passive MPC Proposal 2

181 This proposal uses the same objective function eq. (38) as the traditional MPC.

182 5.3. Constraints on the Objective Function of the Passive MPC Proposal 2

183 Linear constraints in the traditional MPC (eq. (40)) allow to estimate PTO force increments
 184 $\underline{\Delta \mathbf{F}}_{pto}(k)$ over the prediction horizon, limiting the variation range of the position $(x_{pto}^{min}, x_{pto}^{max})$, velocity
 185 $(v_{pto}^{min}, v_{pto}^{max})$ and force of the PTO $(F_{pto}^{min}, F_{pto}^{max})$ by setting maximum and minimum values in the vector
 186 $\underline{\mathbf{V}}(k)$ (eq. (29)). Generally, these limits are constants over the prediction horizon and for all time
 187 instants k , hence, the elements of the vectors $\underline{\mathbf{V}}(k)^{min}$ and $\underline{\mathbf{V}}(k)^{max}$ defined in eq. (40) will be:

$$\underline{\mathbf{V}}(k)^{max} = \begin{bmatrix} (x_{pto}^{max}, v_{pto}^{max}, F_{pto}^{max})^T \\ (x_{pto}^{max}, v_{pto}^{max}, F_{pto}^{max})^T \\ (x_{pto}^{max}, v_{pto}^{max}, F_{pto}^{max})^T \\ \vdots \\ (x_{pto}^{max}, v_{pto}^{max}, F_{pto}^{max})^T \end{bmatrix}, \quad \underline{\mathbf{V}}(k)^{min} = \begin{bmatrix} (x_{pto}^{min}, v_{pto}^{min}, F_{pto}^{min})^T \\ (x_{pto}^{min}, v_{pto}^{min}, F_{pto}^{min})^T \\ (x_{pto}^{min}, v_{pto}^{min}, F_{pto}^{min})^T \\ \vdots \\ (x_{pto}^{min}, v_{pto}^{min}, F_{pto}^{min})^T \end{bmatrix} \quad (59)$$

188 In order to set a passive MPC strategy that handles the linear constraints, maximum and minimum
 189 values of eq. (59) must be considered as variants over the prediction horizon and for every time instant
 190 k :

$$\underline{\mathbf{V}}(k)^{max} = \begin{bmatrix} (x_{pto}^{max}(k+1), v_{pto}^{max}(k+1), F_{pto}^{max}(k+1))^T \\ (x_{pto}^{max}(k+2), v_{pto}^{max}(k+2), F_{pto}^{max}(k+2))^T \\ (x_{pto}^{max}(k+3), v_{pto}^{max}(k+3), F_{pto}^{max}(k+3))^T \\ \vdots \\ (x_{pto}^{max}(k+n_h), v_{pto}^{max}(k+n_h), F_{pto}^{max}(k+n_h))^T \end{bmatrix} \quad (60)$$

191

$$\underline{\mathbf{V}}(k)^{min} = \begin{bmatrix} (x_{pto}^{min}(k+1), v_{pto}^{min}(k+1), F_{pto}^{min}(k+1))^T \\ (x_{pto}^{min}(k+2), v_{pto}^{min}(k+2), F_{pto}^{min}(k+2))^T \\ (x_{pto}^{min}(k+3), v_{pto}^{min}(k+3), F_{pto}^{min}(k+3))^T \\ \vdots \\ (x_{pto}^{min}(k+n_h), v_{pto}^{min}(k+n_h), F_{pto}^{min}(k+n_h))^T \end{bmatrix} \quad (61)$$

The idea is to find values to the elements of the matrices in eqs. (60) and (61) that impose unidirectional power flow on the PTO. Traditional passive control can provide these values in a fast way. Following, a generic set of PTO velocities $\underline{\mathbf{v}}_{pto}^{ref}(k)$ and PTO forces $\underline{\mathbf{F}}_{pto}^{ref}(k)$ obtained by applying passive control ($\underline{\mathbf{F}}_{pto}^{ref}(k) = b_{pto} \underline{\mathbf{v}}_{pto}^{ref}(k)$) over the prediction horizon at time instant k is presented:

$$\underline{\mathbf{v}}_{pto}^{ref}(k) = \begin{bmatrix} v_{pto}^{ref}(k+1) & v_{pto}^{ref}(k+2) & v_{pto}^{ref}(k+3) & \dots & v_{pto}^{ref}(k+n_h) \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (62)$$

$$\underline{\mathbf{F}}_{pto}^{ref}(k) = b_{pto} \begin{bmatrix} v_{pto}^{ref}(k+1) & v_{pto}^{ref}(k+2) & v_{pto}^{ref}(k+3) & \dots & v_{pto}^{ref}(k+n_h) \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (63)$$

or

$$\underline{\mathbf{v}}_{pto}^{ref}(k) = \begin{bmatrix} v_{pto}^{ref}(k+i) \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n_h \quad (64)$$

$$\underline{\mathbf{F}}_{pto}^{ref}(k) = \begin{bmatrix} F_{pto}^{ref}(k+i) \end{bmatrix} = b_{pto} \begin{bmatrix} v_{pto}^{ref}(k+i) \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n_h \quad (65)$$

192 This passive MPC proposal, by adapting linear constraints to the traditional MPC to get passivity,
 193 is based on setting PTO velocity and force constraints, according to the signs of the same signals found
 194 applying passive control.

195 In this sense, the procedure will start getting results applying passive control over a prediction
 196 horizon and at a time instant k (eqs. (64) and (65)) to ensure positive values of the PTO power over
 197 such prediction horizon at time instant k in the MPC. Then, the sign of the PTO velocity at each instant
 198 $(k+i)$ is evaluated. If the PTO velocity $v_{pto}^{ref}(k+i)$ is positive, the PTO velocity and the PTO force
 199 in the MPC at the time instant $(k+i)$ are constrained to take positive values between zero and the
 200 maximum positive values $\alpha v_{pto}^{ref}(k+i)$ and $\beta F_{pto}^{ref}(k+i)$ respectively, being α and β positive constants.
 201 On the other hand, if the PTO velocity $v_{pto}^{ref}(k+i)$ is negative, then the PTO velocity and the PTO
 202 force in the MPC at the time instant $(k+i)$ are constrained to take negative values between zero and
 203 the minimum negative values $\alpha v_{pto}^{ref}(k+i)$ and $\beta F_{pto}^{ref}(k+i)$. Summarizing, maximum and minimum
 204 values in eqs. (60) and (61) will be set according to the following procedure:

- 205 1. At the time instant k , the prediction horizon is the set $H = \{(k+i)/i = 1, 2, \dots, n_h\}$
- 206 2. Passive control with PTO damping b_{pto} is executed over the prediction horizon H obtaining the
 207 velocity series $\{v_{pto}^{ref}(k+i)/i = 1, 2, \dots, n_h\}$

3. Linear constraints of the MPC are assigned at each time instant $(k + i)$ over H :

For $i = 1, 2, \dots, n_h$

- If $v_{pto}^{ref}(k + i) > 0$

$$\begin{aligned} x_{pto}^{max}(k + i) &= x_{pto}^{max} \\ v_{pto}^{max}(k + i) &= \alpha v_{pto}^{ref}(k + i) \\ F_{pto}^{max}(k + i) &= \beta b_{pto} v_{pto}^{ref}(k + i) \\ x_{pto}^{min}(k + i) &= x_{pto}^{min} \\ v_{pto}^{min}(k + i) &= 0 \\ F_{pto}^{min}(k + i) &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

- If $v_{pto}^{ref}(k + i) < 0$

$$\begin{aligned} x_{pto}^{max}(k + i) &= x_{pto}^{max} \\ v_{pto}^{max}(k + i) &= 0 \\ F_{pto}^{max}(k + i) &= 0 \\ x_{pto}^{min}(k + i) &= x_{pto}^{min} \\ v_{pto}^{min}(k + i) &= \alpha v_{pto}^{ref}(k + i) \\ F_{pto}^{min}(k + i) &= \beta b_{pto} v_{pto}^{ref}(k + i) \end{aligned}$$

This way of constraining velocity and force of the PTO will guarantee unidirectional power flow from the WEC to the PTO when MPC is applied.

6. Numerical Analysis

The WEC of Fig. 1 is a the two-body self-referenced point absorber formed by an external floater ring with a 19.2 m diameter and 4.8 m height that moves with respect to an internal cylindrical spar with a 5.7 m diameter and 36.5 m height attached to the sea bed by means of a mooring. This WEC is inspired by the Ocean Power Technology (OPT) PowerBuoyTM. Similar two-body WECs are researched in [24] as RM3 and in the NumWEC project [25] as F-2HB. The two-body WEC model used in this work is described in more detail in appendix A.

The time-domain simulation model of the two-body WEC shown in Fig. 1, has been implemented in Matlab/Simulink in order to test the proposed control strategies. The model is formed by three main subsystems: The first subsystem generates the excitation force, the second one models the WEC using a state space equations and the last one implements the control strategy and sets the PTO force.

The Wamit program was used to calculate the hydrodynamic parameters as functions of the frequency. The irregular wave profiles were generated randomly using the Bretschneider spectrum. For each peak period considered, a 15 min simulation was executed. The time step used in all MPC strategies is 0.05 s and the prediction horizon is 9 s. In addition, in order to focus on the control strategy [11], it is assumed that the future excitation wave forces are perfectly known (exact prediction of the excitation forces) over the prediction horizon.

The results applying the passive MPC proposal 1 of section 4 (P-MPC-1) and the passive MPC proposal 2 of section 5 (P-MPC-2) are compared with those obtained through the traditional MPC without constraints of section 3.2 (MPC), passive MPC with nonlinear constraint (P-MPC-NLC) of section 3.4 (eq. (41)) and passive (i.e. resistive) loading control (RL).

In addition, the MPC strategy with relaxed linear constraints of section 3.3 (eqs. (39) and (40)) has been included in order to consider the computational effort when linear restrictions are added (MPC-LC). In this case, the relaxed constraints are maximum excursion: 5 m, maximum speed: 5 m/s and maximum PTO force: 10 MN. It is important to highlight that these relaxed constraints aren't

239 achieved during the simulations and are only considered to estimate the processing time when linear
240 constraints are added to the MPC.

241 Also, an optimal passive strategy (ORL) with PTO constant damping has been included as
242 reference control where the best PTO damping in terms of power extracted is obtained by means of an
243 optimization process on the same wave profile. These strategies are explained briefly in appendix B.

244 Taking into account that the proposal P-MPC-1 had good performances compared to RL and ORL
245 strategies, it was used in the step 3 of the algorithm in section 5.3 as starting point of the P-MPC-2.
246 Further, the constants α and β in step 4 of the same algorithm were set to 3 and 2.25, respectively and
247 the excursion constraints were set to $x_{pto}^{max} = 2.5$ m and $x_{pto}^{min} = -2.5$ m. The selection of α and β affects
248 the processing time of the P-MPC-2 and it was performed to set constraints for the speed and the PTO
249 force that are non achieved, but close to the maximum obtained.

250 In order to conveniently compare the control strategies, the maximum number of iterations in
251 the optimization problem associated to the control P-MPC-2 and P-MPC-NLC was adjusted in order
252 to obtain processing times in the same range as the control MPC-LC (less than 1 s). In this sense, the
253 number of iterations in the control P-MPC-2 and P-MPC-NLC were 5 and 50 respectively. Besides, for
254 the other control strategies the maximum number of iterations used was the value set by default (250)
255 in the Matlab function of the optimization problem.

256 6.1. Relevant average and maximum results

257 This section presents the relevant results considering irregular waves, varying the peak period
258 from 5 s to 16 s and considering significant wave heights of 1.25 m, 3.25 m and 5.25 m. **The seed to
259 create each wave profile was changed. This means that the wave profiles are not the scaled version of
260 each other.**

261 Fig. 3 shows the average PTO power for all considered wave profiles and for the control strategies
262 RL, ORL, MPC, P-MPC-1, P-MPC-2, P-MPC-NLC and MPC-LC described above. It can be noted that
263 the traditional MPC strategies (MPC and MPC-LC) allow higher average power absorption due to
264 their reactive nature. This means that the energy is circulating in a bidirectional way between the PTO
265 and the WEC.

266 On the other hand, the control strategy P-MPC-2 presents better performances than P-MPC-1 in
267 terms of extracted power. The reason is that P-MPC-1 is a simple and faster strategy that keeps the
268 same PTO damping over the entire prediction horizon, while P-MPC-2 has to estimate the PTO force
269 for each time instant over the prediction horizon being more complex and slower.

270 Taking into account the differences in processing time and the power extracted between both
271 proposed control strategies P-MPC-1 and P-MPC-2, it is convenient to divide the analysis in two
272 groups. The first group is composed by faster control strategies with lower extracted power (P-MPC-1,
273 RL and ORL), and the second one is composed by slower control strategies with higher extracted
274 power (P-MPC-2 and P-MPC-NLC). A third group formed by the reactive control strategies with the
275 greatest extracted power (MPC and MPC-LC) will serve as reference for the first and second group.
276 The MPC strategy without constraints is a convex quadratic programming problem whose solution is
277 fast in terms of processing time. For this reason the first group will be compared to the MPC strategy.
278 Besides, the MPC-LC strategy considers the computational effort when linear restrictions are added.
279 These linear constraints are relaxed, never achieved and added to estimate the processing time in the
280 quadratic programming problem with linear constraints (non-convex programming problem). For
281 this reason the second group, formed by control strategies, for which passivity is defined in their
282 constraints, will be compared to the MPC-LC strategy.

283 Based on Fig. 3 it can be concluded that the proposal P-MPC-1 extracts 5% more average power
284 than the RL strategy and practically the same average power as the ORL reference strategy. On the
285 other hand, the proposal P-MPC-2 allows to obtain 4% more power than the strategy P-MPC-NLC.

Figure 3. Average PTO power in irregular wave varying the peak period T_p from 4 s to 16 s for significance high a) $H_s=1.25$ m, b) $H_s=3.25$ m and c) $H_s=5.25$ m

Figure 4. Average processing time in irregular wave varying the peak period T_p from 4 s to 16 s for significance high a) $H_s=1.25$ m, b) $H_s=3.25$ m and c) $H_s=5.25$ m

286 Concerning the average processing time to solve the associated optimization problem, Fig. 4
 287 shows that the most time-consuming control strategy is P-MPC-NLC (0.973 s), followed in descending order
 288 order by MPC-LC (0.844 s), P-MPC-2 (0.661 s), P-MPC-1 (0.029 s) and MPC (0.013 s). It can be
 289 highlighted that the processing time of P-MPC-1 is low and in the same order as MPC. On the other
 290 hand, the processing time of the control strategy P-MPC-2 is 32% lower than P-MPC-NLC and 22%
 291 lower than MPC-LC. According to the results reported in Figs. 3 and 4 both proposals are competitive
 292 in terms of absorbed power and processing time.

293 Fig. 5 shows that the maximum speed takes high values for MPC and P-MPC-NLC, low values
 294 for the control RL and ORL and intermediate values for both proposals P-MPC-1 and P-MPC-2.

295 Fig. 6 presents the maximum PTO force values for all control strategies and wave profiles. This
 296 figure shows that the maximum PTO force takes low values when applying P-MPC-1, and intermediate
 297 values similar to the P-MPC-NLC case, when applying P-MPC-2.

298 Summarizing, the control strategy P-MPC-2 extracts more power than P-MPC-NLC consuming
 299 less processing time, with intermediate values (between group 1 and group 3) of the maximum speed
 300 and PTO force. On the other hand, the control strategy P-MPC-1 extracts similar power as the reference
 301 control strategy ORL, requiring processing time in the same order as MPC.

Figure 5. Maximum speed in irregular wave varying the peak period T_p from 4 s to 16 s for significance high a) $H_s=1.25$ m, b) $H_s=3.25$ m and c) $H_s=5.25$ m

Figure 6. Maximum PTO force in irregular wave varying the peak period T_p from 4 s to 16 s for significance high a) $H_s=1.25$ m, b) $H_s=3.25$ m and c) $H_s=5.25$ m

302 6.2. Relevant time signals

303 This section presents the relevant waveforms (position, speed, PTO force and PTO power) for the control strategies RL, ORL and both proposals P-MPC-1 and P-MPC-2 in irregular waves with
 304 peak period $T_p=12$ s and significance wave height 3.25 m. In order to highlight the difference between
 305 the waveforms obtained, they are shown in a 70s-time window from the time instant 30 s to the time
 306 instant 100 s.

308 In Fig. 7 higher position and speed values in the control strategies P-MPC-1 and P-MPC-2
 309 compared to RL and ORL can be noted. On the other hand, in Fig. 8 lower PTO force and higher
 310 PTO power can be observed in both proposals. The noise in the PTO force and power waveforms in
 311 proposal P-MPC-2 is due to the values of the PTO damping time series obtained during successive
 312 optimization results.

Figure 7. Position (a) and speed (b) of the PTO for the sea state $T_p=12$ s and $H_s=3.25$ m

Figure 8. Force (a) and power (b) of the PTO for the sea state $T_p=12$ s and $H_s=3.25$ m

313 Fig. 9 presents the values of the PTO damping as a function of time. It can be noted that the
 314 values in both P-MPC-1 and P-MPC-2 vary over time while the PTO damping in the RL and ORL
 315 strategies is constant. In addition, the PTO damping in P-MPC-1 presents less abrupt changes and
 316 lower values compared to P-MPC-2. The reason of this is that P-MPC-1 is based on keeping the PTO
 317 damping constant over the prediction horizon, while P-MPC-2 estimates a different PTO damping for
 318 each time instant over the prediction horizon.

Figure 9. PTO damping for the sea state $T_p=12$ s and $H_s=3.25$ m

319 6.3. Sensitivity analysis

320 Fig. 10 presents the performance of P-MPC-2 and P-MPC-NLP in terms of average power extracted
 321 by the PTO as a function of the average time consumed to solve the optimization problem in each time
 322 instant.

Figure 10. PTO damping for the sea state $T_p=12$ s and $H_s=3.25$ m

323 In order to vary the processing time, the number of iterations was increased conveniently on
 324 both strategies. The wave profile used in this analysis is the sea state with peak period $T_p=12$ s and
 325 significant wave height $H_s=3.25$ m.

326 In Fig. 10 it can be noted that a higher average power is obtained applying P-MPC-2, when the
 327 average time spent in the optimization problem is less than 1.15 s., while P-MPC-NLC extracted more
 328 power for a higher processing times (greater than 1.15 s).

329 Since real-time control requires fast response from the processors in order to get an estimation
 330 of the control action, the control strategy P-MPC-NLC is not feasible from a technical point of view.
 331 On the other hand, as the proposal P-MPC-2 consumed less processing time extracting more average
 332 power, it could be suitable for real time implementation.

333 7. Conclusions

334 This work proposes two passive MPC control strategies applied to a two-body self-reference point
 335 absorber. The first proposal adapts the MPC formulation to a passive loading strategy (P-MPC-1) and
 336 the second one adapts the linear constraints in the MPC in order to allow only unidirectional power
 337 flow between the wave energy converter and the power take-off (P-MPC-2).

338 The results show that the first proposal has a processing time in the same order (0.029 s) as the
 339 MPC without constraints (0.013 s), extracting 5% more power than the resistive loading (RL) and 0.1%
 340 more power than the passive reference control strategy (ORL), achieving intermediate values for PTO
 341 speed and low values for PTO force.

342 On the other hand, the second proposal obtains 4% more average power than the passive MPC
 343 strategy with non-linear constraints, consuming 32% less processing time than the passive MPC
 344 strategy with non-linear constraints and 22% less processing time than MPC with linear constraints. In
 345 addition, this proposal presents intermediate values to the maximum speed and the PTO force.

346 Due to its low processing time, the first proposal P-MPC-1 could be used to improve the
 347 performance of the traditional passive control (RL) including constraint. In this sense, in this article
 348 the first proposal is used to initialize the second proposal. On the other hand, the second proposal
 349 could be used to implement a technically feasible passive MPC.

350 **As an MPC strategy, our proposals are very dependent on the model used in their formulation as**
 351 **well as on the prediction of the excitation force. A non-representative model of the WEC would lead to**
 352 **an inefficient MPC strategy.**

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360 **Conflicts of Interest:** The authors declare no conflict of interest.

361 Abbreviations

362 The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

363	MPC	Model Predictive Control
	WEC	Wave Energy Converter
	QP	Quadratic Programming
	PTO	Power Take-Off
	NLP	Nonlinear Programming
364	P-MPC-1	Passive MPC Proposal 1
	P-MPC-2	Passive MPC Proposal 2
	P-MPC-NLC	MPC with Nonlinear Constraint
	RL	Passive Control
	MPC-LC	MPC with Linear Constraint
	ORL	Optimal Passive Control

365 Appendix A

366 The WEC of Fig. 1 is a the two-body self-reference point absorber formed by an external floater
 367 ring with a 19.2 m diameter and 4.8 m height that moves with respect to an internal cylindrical spar
 368 with a 5.7 m diameter and 36.5 m height attached to the sea bed by means of a mooring. The drafts of
 369 the floater and spar are 2.8 m and 28.8 m, respectively. The heave plate in the submerged extreme of
 370 the spar has diameter of 28.8 m and height 0.1 m. The floater and the spar have the following values:
 371 masses 661 t and 799.7 t, hydrostatic coefficients 2640.9 kN/m and 260.3 kN/m, viscosity coefficients
 372 104 kN.s/m and 78 kN.s/m and infinity masses 1101.7 t and 7995.3 t. The value of the PTO friction
 373 coefficient is 82.4 kN.s/m and the stiffness of the mooring is 10 kN/m. The PTO mass is negligible
 374 compared to the mass of the floater and spar.

Both radiation forces $F_{r1}(t)$ and $F_{r2}(t)$ have been modeled by means of state space equations using third and second degree systems:

$$\dot{\mathbf{U}}_1(t) = \mathbf{A}_{r1}\mathbf{U}_1(t) + \mathbf{B}_{r1}\dot{z}_1(t) \quad (\text{A1})$$

$$F_{r1}(t) = \mathbf{C}_{r1}\mathbf{U}_1(t) \quad (\text{A2})$$

where

$$\mathbf{A}_{r1} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.7418 & -1.0937 & 0.8431 \\ 1.0937 & -0.0070 & 0.0466 \\ -0.8431 & 0.0466 & -0.4280 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{B}_{r1} = \begin{bmatrix} -3.9929 \\ 0.3634 \\ -1.6030 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A3})$$

$$\mathbf{C}_{r1}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} -1.3642 & -0.1241 & 0.5477 \end{bmatrix} 10^5 \quad (\text{A4})$$

and

$$\dot{\mathbf{U}}_2(t) = \mathbf{A}_{r2}\mathbf{U}_2(t) + \mathbf{B}_{r2}\dot{z}_2(t) \quad (\text{A5})$$

$$F_{r2}(t) = \mathbf{C}_{r2}\mathbf{U}_2(t) \quad (\text{A6})$$

where

$$\mathbf{A}_{r2} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.4260 & 0.7843 \\ -0.7843 & -0.00004 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{B}_{r2} = \begin{bmatrix} -1.2278 \\ -0.0121 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A7})$$

$$\mathbf{C}_{r2} = \begin{bmatrix} -4.1950 & 0.0414 \end{bmatrix} 10^4 \quad (\text{A8})$$

375 The dynamics of the system has been modeled by means of the following state space equations:

$$\dot{\mathbf{X}}(t) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{X}(t) + \mathbf{B}_{e1}F_{e1}(t) + \mathbf{B}_{e2}F_{e2}(t) + \mathbf{B}_{pto}F_{pto}(t) \quad (\text{A9})$$

$$\mathbf{Y}(t) = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{X}(t) = [z_1(t) - z_2(t) \quad z_1(t) - \dot{z}_2(t)]^T \quad (\text{A10})$$

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.7418 & -1.0937 & 0.8431 & 0 & -3.9929 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1.0937 & -0.0070 & 0.0466 & 0 & 0.3634 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.8431 & 0.0466 & -0.4280 & 0 & -1.6030 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.0774 & 0.0070 & -0.0311 & -1.4982 & -0.1057 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.0468 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -0.4260 & 0.7843 & 0 & -1.2278 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -0.7843 & -0.00004 & 0 & -0.0121 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.0094 & 0.0048 & -0.00005 & -0.0307 & -0.0979 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A11})$$

$$\mathbf{B}_{e1} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.5673 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}^T 10^{-6} \quad (\text{A12})$$

$$\mathbf{B}_{e2} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.1137 \end{bmatrix}^T 10^{-6} \quad (\text{A13})$$

$$\mathbf{B}_{pto} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.5673 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -0.1137 \end{bmatrix}^T 10^{-6} \quad (\text{A14})$$

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A15})$$

376 Appendix B

377 Following, all control strategies used in this paper are explained briefly and summarized in table
378 [A1](#):

- The passive control strategy (RL) considers the PTO force proportional to the speed.

$$F_{pto}(t) = |Z_{th}(\omega_p)|(z_1(t) - \dot{z}_2(t)) \quad (\text{A16})$$

379 where $Z_{th}(\omega) = R_{th}(\omega) + jX_{th}(\omega)$ is the Thevenin impedance seen from the PTO in the WEC
380 electrical representation and ω_p is the wave peak frequency.

- 381 • Optimal passive strategy (ORL) has been included as reference control. This control estimates
382 the best PTO damping in terms of power extracted by means of an optimization process on the
383 same wave profile. The ORL requires to know the entire time series of the wave over the analysis
384 interval. The ORL control strategy is applied only to get a reference to the maximum power
385 extracted by the constant PTO damping passive control.
- 386 • Traditional MPC has been included in order to compare PTO power and processing time results.
- 387 • Traditional MPC with relaxed linear constraints (MPC-LC) has been included to estimate how
388 the processing time changes when linear constraints are included in traditional MPC. "Relaxed
389 linear constraints" means that such restrictions are not achieved.
- 390 • Including nonlinear constraints in the traditional MPC (P-MPC-NLC) is the most common way
391 to get passivity in MPC. The drawback is that it is expensive from a computational point of view.

Table A1. Summary of the control strategies applied in the article

Control Strategy	Description	Problem	Matlab solver	Constraints	Algorithm
MPC	Traditional MPC	QP	quadprog	No	interior-point-convex
P-MPC-1	Passive MPC proposal 1	NLP	fminsearch	No	Nelder-Mead simplex
P-MPC-2	Passive MPC proposal 2	QP	quadprog	Linear	interior-point-convex
RL	Traditional passive	-	-	-	-
ORL	Reference optimal passive	-	-	-	-
P-MPC-NLC	Reference passive MPC	NLP	fmincon	NLC	sequential quadratic programming
MPC-LC	Traditional MPC with relaxed linear constraints	QP	quadprog	Linear	interior-point-convex

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